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ROLE OF HYDROPHILIC POLYMERS ON THE STABILITY OF FORMULATIONS OF TENOXICAM – SBE₇-β-CD INCLUSION COMPLEX

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out to evaluate the usefulness of sulfobutyl ether β-Cyclodextrin (SBE₇-β-CD) in increasing the dissolution rate of tenoxicam. The approach employed to prepare the inclusion complexes of the drug with captisol is by freeze drying and kneading methods. The phase solubility studies indicated that a 1:1 M complex was formed between tenoxicam and captisol. The complexes showed a rapid dissolution compared to the pure drug tenoxicam. In between the kneaded and freeze dried complexes, the freeze dried complex showed higher dissolution rate. The inclusion complexes were evaluated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). The drug is found to exist in amorphous state in the complexes. The efficacy of hydrophilic polymers, gelucire and hydroxypropyl cellulose in stabilizing the high dissolving amorphous forms of tenoxicam in the tablet formulations was studied and the findings of the investigation suggested that the hydrophilic polymers were able to offer protection in preventing the transformation of the amorphous drug during compression and storage. It can be concluded from the results of the present study that careful formulation is essential to stabilize the high dissolving forms of drugs to retain their physical stability and high dissolution characteristics.

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INTRODUCTION

Tenoxicam is 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-*N*-(2-pyridyl)-2-Hthieno [2, 3e] [1,2] thiazine-3-carboxamide-1,1-dioxide [1]. It is used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis at an oral dose of 20 mg [2]. It is a crystalline and biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS) class II drug and is very slightly soluble in water (0.072 mg / ml). Drugs with low solubility show poor bioavailability after oral administration and their absorption is dissolution rate limited. Complexation and solid dispersion technology are two widely employed approaches to increase the dissolution of poorly soluble drugs. There are reports of formation of inclusion complex with beta cyclodextrin for improving the dissolution of tenoxicam [3]. In another investigation, solvent deposited systems of tenoxicam on microcrystalline cellulose are prepared to enhance the dissolution [4].

Sulfobutyl ether β -Cyclodextrin (SBE₇- β -CD) is a chemically modified β - cyclodextrin that is a cyclic hydrophilic oligosaccharide. It is commercially available as captisol. It is a highly water-soluble derivative of β -cyclodextrin. Pre-clinical and clinical studies have been performed and indicate that captisol is safe when administered parenterally or orally and does not exhibit the nephrotoxicity associated with beta-cyclodextrin. Relative to beta-cyclodextrin, captisol has superior water solubility in excess of 100 grams/100 ml, a 50-fold improvement [5]

There are reports of utility captisol in improving the solubility of drugs for development of mainly parenteral dosage forms and some solid dosage forms [6-8]. The usefulness of SBE₇- β -CD in improving the dissolution rate of tenoxicam is not reported. So in the present investigation, formation of an inclusion complex between tenoxicam and SBE₇ β -CD was studied. The complexes were prepared by kneading and freeze drying methods. The prepared complexes are characterized by x – ray diffraction, differential scanning calorimetry, infrared spectroscopy and dissolutions studies.

In many previous investigations with captisol, the increase in dissolution of poorly soluble drugs was attributed to the decrease in crystalline state of the drug and conversion to an amorphous form [9]. However, these high dissolving amorphous forms of drugs are inherently unstable and can revert back to the original crystalline form particularly during tableting and other related processes [10].

This is in fact a major constraint in processing of formulations of solid dispersions or inclusion complexes. Development of solid dispersion into convenient dosage form with desirable stability characteristics is a major challenge for pharmaceutical scientists. Since the quality and performance of a pharmaceutical solid formulation depend on solid state of the drug and excipients, a thorough investigation of potential processing-induced transformations (PITs) of the ingredients is required. Various studies are made to evaluate the presence of excipients on the fast dissolving forms in formulation in an attempt to arrest the polymorphic transformation in formulations. Schmidt et al reported that inclusion of polyethylene oxide in tablets and mixtures of amorphous indomethacin has significantly reduced recrystallization [11]. In another study, Mirza et al observed that inclusion of polyethylene glycol in the formulation of erythromycin solid dispersion polymer caused the drug to undergo multiple phase transformations [12]. In a study it is reported that stabilization of amorphous form of etoricoxib is possible in the melt granules with low amount of polyglycolized glycerides [13].

In the present study, the role of 2 hydrophilic polymers gelucire (50/13) and hydroxypropyl cellulose on the stabilization of prepared tenoxicam - captisol complex in tablet formulations and during storage is investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Tenoxicam (TX), a gift sample from Julphar Gulf Pharmaceutical Industries, UAE. Sulfobutyl ether β -Cyclodextrin (SBE₇- β -CD) [Captisol] is provided by Cydex Corprn, USA. Gelucire (50/13), Gattefosse, France (sample given by Genova Life Sciences, Bengaluru), Hydroxy propyl cellulose, Nisso; viscosity of 3-5.9 in 2% w/w solution; all other chemicals and reagents are of analytical grade.

Phase Solubility Studies

The influence of captisol on the solubility of tenoxicam was evaluated using the method reported by Higuchi and Connors [14]. Excess amounts of tenoxicam (50 mg) were added to 15 ml of distilled water containing increasing concentrations of SBE₇- β -CD (2–16 mM) in 25 ml stoppered glass bottles. The obtained suspensions were shaken at 25 \pm 0.5°C for 3 days in a temperature controlled shaking water bath (Labtech Model LSB-015S). After equilibration, aliquots were withdrawn, filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter, and assayed for tenoxicam content by measuring the absorbance at 368 nm employing UV Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu Model UV 1800).

Each experiment was carried out in triplicate. Solubility diagrams were constructed by plotting the molar concentration of tenoxicam dissolved (solubility) versus the molar concentration of the CD. From these diagrams, the stability constant for the complexation of tenoxicam with captisol was calculated by employing the formula:

$$K_s = \left(\frac{\text{Slope}}{S_0(1 - \text{Slope})} \right)$$

The slope is obtained from the graph (Fig 1) and S_0 is the equilibrium solubility of tenoxicam.

Preparation of tenoxicam and SBE- β -CD inclusion complexes

The complexes are prepared by 2 methods, Kneading Method (KN) and Freeze-Drying Method (FD) in a 1:1 M ratio. The two different methods employed for the preparation of solid complexes are described below:

Kneading Method (KN)

The calculated amounts of TX and SBE₇ β-CD were accurately weighed, transferred to a mortar, and kneaded for 45 min. During this process, a small volume of methanol: water (50:50 v/v) solution was added to the mixture to maintain a suitable consistency. The final product was dried at 40°C for 48 h and then was ground to powder, passed through a 100-mesh sieve, and stored in a sealed glass vial until further use.

Freeze-Drying Method (FD)

A 1:1 M ratio of TX and SBE₇ β-CD were dissolved in methanol and distilled water, respectively. The resulting solutions were mixed for 24 h at 25°C using a magnetic stirrer. The final solution was frozen at -70°C, and subsequently freeze-dried for 48 h at -50°C using a freeze-dryer (Southern Scientific, Model LFD 07). The lyophilized powder was passed through a 100-mesh sieve and stored in a sealed glass vial until further use.

Characterization of tenoxicam and SBE₇ β-CD inclusion complexes

Dissolution Studies

The dissolution tenoxicam in pure form and from the complexes was studied using USP Type II dissolution rate test apparatus (Lab India Model DISSO) employing a paddle stirrer. In 900 ml of dissolution medium (0.1 N hydrochloric acid), a sample equivalent to 20 mg of tenoxicam was added and a speed of 50 rpm and a temperature of 37°C ± 1°C were employed in each test. A 5 ml aliquot of dissolution medium was withdrawn at different time intervals, filtered, suitably diluted and assayed spectrophotometrically at 368 nm using Shimadzu Model UV 1800 spectrophotometer. The percent of tenoxicam dissolved at various time intervals was calculated and plotted against time. The results are given in Table 1 and shown in Fig 2

X-ray diffraction

X-ray powder diffraction patterns of tenoxicam and complexes were obtained by using X-ray powder diffractometer, PANalytical, Model No. X Pert pro employing Cu K_α radiation. The diffractograms were run between 2° and 40° at 2°/min in terms of 2θ angle. The operation data were as follows: generator tension (voltage) 40 kV; generator current 30 mA. The diffractograms of tenoxicam and complexes are shown in Fig.3.

Differential scanning calorimetry

Tenoxicam and the complexes were subjected to differential scanning calorimetric analysis to know about the physical state of the drug in the complex and any interaction between the drug and complexing agent. The calorimeter (TA Instruments, Bangalore Model Q 20) was operated at a scanning rate of 10°C per minute and heated between 25°C to 350°C. The samples were sealed in aluminum pans and heated in a constant inert atmosphere maintained by purging nitrogen gas at a flow rate of 10 ml/min. The thermograms obtained on various products are shown in Fig. 4.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

Tenoxicam and the complexes prepared were subjected to FTIR analysis using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (Agilent Model Cary 630). Attenuated total reflectance (ATR) sampling interface was used to obtain the spectra. The IR spectra are shown in Fig. 5.

Preparation of tablets

The tablets employing the inclusion complex are prepared by either direct compression or by melt granulation when the formulation contained gelucire (50/13). The details of the formulations are shown in Table 2

Direct compression

The complex equivalent to 20 mg of tenoxicam was mixed in geometric proportions with the other ingredients of the formula in a closed dry plastic container and the blend was screened and compressed on Cadmach (Model No: CMD₃-D16) rotary punching machine.

Melt granulation

Preparation of Granules

Granules of tenoxicam were prepared using the melt granulation technique. The complex: gelucire ratios used to prepare the granules were either 1: 0.5 or 1:0.25 parts by weight. Gelucire was melted at 55 °C. To the molten gelucire, the complex was added, mixed well and then cooled to room temperature to obtain the solid mass. The mass was passed through sieve No. 35 to obtain uniform sized granules. The granules are now further blended with the rest of the ingredients of the formulation and compressed.

Evaluation of tablet Parameters

Tablets were evaluated for drug content, uniformity of weight, hardness (Tab Machines) friability (Veego Model VFT 2D) and dissolution and the results are shown in Table 3

Stability Study

The products are kept in glass bottles which are closed with a rubber closure and kept in a stability chamber (Newtronic Model No. NLHC8SE) and are exposed to a temperature of 45°C and humidity of 70 ± 5% for 3 months. At the end of 3 months the products were removed and characterized by dissolution and reappearance of crystallinity by XRD studies. Physical parameters like hardness, friability and disintegration time were also evaluated. The results are given in Table 4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase Solubility Studies

The phase solubility plot for TX and SBE₇ β-CD is shown in Fig. 1. It is evident that solubility of TX increased linearly with increase in concentration of SBE₇ β-CD. Correlation coefficient, “r” was found to be 0.9961. The phase solubility diagram can be classified as Type A_L according to Higuchi and Connors. As the slope of the line was less than unity, it can be assumed that the increase in solubility was due to formation of a 1:1 M inclusion complex. The apparent stability constant (K_s) is found to be 1312 M⁻¹. It is reported that cyclodextrin/drug complexes with the values of stability constant in the range of 200 to 5,000 M⁻¹ yield improvement in oral bioavailability [15].

Fig 1 Phase solubility diagrams of Tenoxicam with SBE-β-CD and HP-β-CD in distilled water. [Tenoxicam solubility (M x 10⁻⁶)] - Solubility determined in distilled water.

Characterization of tenoxicam and SBE-β-CD inclusion complexes

Dissolution Studies

The results of the in vitro dissolution profiles of pure drug tenoxicam and the inclusion complexes are shown in Fig 2 and given in Table 1. It can be seen that the complexes showed a rapid dissolution compared to the pure drug tenoxicam. In between the kneaded and freeze dried complexes, the freeze dried complex showed higher dissolution rate. At the end of 30 minutes, the pure drug showed less than 20% dissolution, the kneaded and freeze dried complexes exhibited 75% and 94% dissolution respectively. The dissolution efficiency (DE₃₀) [16] at 30 minutes was calculated and the values are shown in Table 1. Pure tenoxicam showed DE₃₀ of 8.33 % and the complexes showed 45.71% (KN) and 71.65 % (FD)

The significance of increase in dissolution obtained with the complexes was assessed by calculating the difference (f1) and similarity factors (f2) as per the model proposed by Moore and Flanner [17]. The difference factor f1 is proportional to the average difference between the two profiles, whereas similarity factor f2 is inversely proportional to the average squared difference between the two profiles. Generally, if the f1 values are above 15, then the 2 profiles compared are considered as different. In the present investigation, when the dissolution profile of pure drug is compared with the kneaded and freeze dried complexes, the values are found to be 31.22 and 45.87 respectively.

Fig 2 Dissolution of pure drug and inclusion complexes.

Table 1 Dissolution characteristics of tenoxicam inclusion complexes.

Product	Characteristic *					Difference factor (f1)	Similarity factor (f2)
	Drug content (%)	T ₅₀ (min)	D.E ₃₀ (%)	K ₁ (min ⁻¹) [x 10 ⁻²] (r ²)			
Pure drug (tenoxicam)	--	> 60	8.33	1.31 (0.9862)	--	--	
Freeze dried complex	18.85 ± 0.57	6	71.65	9.91 (0.9865)	45.87	12.11	
Kneaded complex	19.05 ± 0.35	14	45.71	1.62 (0.9798)	31.22	9.25	

D.E. – Dissolution Efficiency

* Average of 3 determinations

Mechanism of increased dissolution from solvent deposited systems

To evaluate the mechanism of involved in the increased dissolution rate of tenoxicam from the complexes, x –ray diffraction and differential scanning calorimetry studies were carried out.

X - ray diffraction

The tenoxicam inclusion complexes were evaluated using x-ray diffraction (Fig 3). The diffractograms of tenoxicam exhibited a series of strong and well-defined peaks which are indicative of the crystalline nature of the drug. Pure SBE₇-β-CD showed a halo-pattern demonstrating amorphous state as evidenced from the absence of diffraction peaks. Similar observations are reported by other authors [18]. In the freeze dried complex, the drug tenoxicam is converted completely into an amorphous form as there is a complete absence of any crystalline peaks. However, in case of kneaded complex, the conversion into amorphous form appears to be partial as some diffractions peaks are still evident. This is also reflected in the lesser dissolution of the drug observed from the kneaded complex compared to the freeze dried complex. So this reduced crystallinity explains the higher dissolution observed from the freeze dried complex.

Fig 3: XRD Spectra of A – Tenoxicam; B – Complex (FD); C- Complex (KN); D- F2 formulation after storage; E- F3 formulation after storage.

Differential scanning calorimetry

The thermograms of tenoxicam and the complexes are shown in Fig 4. The endotherm of pure drug tenoxicam showed a sharp peak at 222°C, which is due to its melting point. An endothermic transformation probably because of a dehydration process was observed between 40 and 100°C in the case of SBE₇-β-CD. Some decomposition related event was noticed at around 275°C in case of SBE₇-β-CD.

For the TX- SBE₇ β-CD freeze dried complex, the characteristic melting point peak of tenoxicam completely disappeared, which suggests some drug– SBE-β-CD interaction resulting in loss of crystallinity of tenoxicam and the drug existing in solid solution state in the complex. Thus the drug remaining in amorphous solid solution state in the cavity of SBE₇ β-CD resulted in enhanced dissolution of tenoxicam. But whereas in the case of kneaded complex an endothermic event can still be noticed which indicates that kneaded method did not result in a complete transformation into amorphous form and entrapment of the drug in the SBE₇ β-CD cavity of the complex. This explains why in the case of kneaded complex the hike in dissolution is less compared to the freeze dried product.

Fig 4: DSC thermograms of A – Tenoxicam; B- Captisol; C – Complex (FD); D- Formulation with Gelucire (after storage); E- Complex (KN).

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FTIR spectroscopy has been carried out to assess the interaction between drug and SBE- β -CD. Fig 5 illustrates the FTIR spectra of tenoxicam, SBE- β -CD, and complexes.

Pure tenoxicam (A) exhibited characteristic peaks at 3119 cm^{-1} and 3092 cm^{-1} (N-H and O-H stretching), 1638 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C stretching), 1598 cm^{-1} and 1530 cm^{-1} (Amide – C = O, C=N), 1436 cm^{-1} (C-H deformation), and 1388 cm^{-1} (C–CH₃ deformation). SBE- β -CD produced absorption peaks at $3,421\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (O–H stretch), $2,938\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–H stretch), and $1,648\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O stretch). All the characteristic peaks of tenoxicam were observed in the molecular inclusion complexes, however there is observed some broadening of bands and a marginal reduction in the intensity of the peaks. These changes suggest that tenoxicam molecule is probably entrapped in the host cavities during the inclusion complexation. No new peaks were detected indicating that there is no chemical interaction in the formed complex.

Fig: 5 IR Spectra of A – TX ; B – Inclusion complex (FD) ; C-Inclusion Complex (KN) ; D – F1 (after storage); E – Captisol ; F – Gelucire.

Preparation of tablets

As the freeze dried complex showed higher dissolution than the kneaded complex, tablets were prepared employing the freeze dried complex. The freeze dried complex was found to be free flowing (flow characteristics not reported here). The different formulations employed are shown in Table 2. The formulations contained 2 hydrophilic polymers, either gelucire or hydroxypropyl cellulose. These polymers were used to study their stabilizing influence on the amorphous drug during compression and storage. Shamkanth Shimpi et al in their study have reported that polyglycolized lipid (gelucire) is able to protect amorphous etoricoxib from undergoing any polymorphic transition during compression [19]. So in the present study, in addition to gelucire, hydroxypropyl cellulose is also evaluated for their ability to prevent any transformation of amorphous tenoxicam to crystalline form. When the formulation (F2) contained gelucire, granules were first prepared by melt granulation and then compressed into tablets whereas in formulation (F3), the blend is directly compressed into tablets.

Table 2 Formulation of tablets employing tenoxicam – captisol complex.

Ingredient (in mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4
Freeze Dried complex equivalent to 20 mg of tenoxicam	106	106	106	106
Gelucire (50/13)	--	53	--	26.5
Hydroxy propyl cellulose	--	--	53	26.5
Lactose	75	22	22	22
Microcrystalline cellulose	25	25	25	25
Sodium starch glycollate	25	25	25	25
Talc	10	10	10	10
Magnesium stearate	10	10	10	10

The post compression properties of the tablets formulated were evaluated. The various prepared tablets were evaluated with respect to their hardness, friability, drug content and weight uniformity and the respective values are shown in Table 3 & 4. The hardness of tablets of all formulations was in the range of 2.71 to 3.27 kg/cm². The friability of tablets of all formulations was less than 1 %. The tablet formulations in all the prepared batches contained tenoxicam within 100 ± 5% of expected content. As such, all the batches of the fabricated tablets were of good quality with regard to hardness, friability and drug content. All tablets are found to be uniform in weight with low standard deviation.

Table 3 Characteristics of tablet formulations before storage.

Formulation	Characteristic					
	Drug content ^a (%)	Hardness ^b (kg /cm ²)	Average weight ^c (mg)	Friability ^d (%)	D.E ₃₀ ^e (%)	K ₁ (min ⁻¹) [x 10 ⁻²] (r ²)
F1	99.45 ± 0.65	2.71± 0.34	249.11 ±0.57	0.68 ±0.19	7.45	1.33 (0.9865)
F2	99.32 ± 1.07	3.05±0.23	250.25± 0.63	0.57±0.14	52.55	3.23 (0.9805)
F3	98.11 ± 0.81	2.98±0.48	251.21 ±0.38	0.65±0.22	42.61	1.51 (0.9820)
F4	99.62 ± 0.77	3.27 ±0.29	249.86±0.54	0.81±0.17	46.12	2.15 (0.9857)

a (n= 10); b (n= 5); c (n= 20); d (n= 20); e (n= 3)

Table 4 Characteristics of tablet formulations after storage.

Formulation	Characteristic					
	Drug content ^a (%)	Hardness ^b (kg/cm ²)	Average weight ^c (mg)	Friability ^d (%)	D.E ₃₀ ^e (%) ^e	K ₁ (min ⁻¹) [x 10 ⁻²] (r ²)
F1	99.12 ± 0.54	2.68 ± 0.27	250.33 ± 0.37	0.71 ± 0.24	7.38	1.03 (0.9821)
F2	100.32 ± 0.75	2.95 ± 0.39	250.25 ± 0.72	0.67 ± 0.19	52.47	2.63 (0.9832)
F3	98.66 ± 0.88	3.11 ± 0.22	251.11 ± 0.45	0.59 ± 0.32	27.56	1.01 (0.9952)
F4	98.44 ± 0.69	3.09 ± 0.41	249.67 ± 0.76	0.77 ± 0.24	43.31	1.87 (0.9812)

a (n= 10); b (n= 5); c (n= 20); d (n= 20); e (n= 3)

The influence of the 2 polymers on the stability of amorphous tenoxicam during compression and storage is evaluated by determining the dissolution of tablets immediately after compression and after storage and by x ray diffraction. The various dissolution parameters of the tablets are given in Table 3 & 4 and shown in Fig 6 & 7. F2 formulation, which contained only gelucire, has shown high dissolution before and after storage whereas F3 formulation, which contained HPC while exhibiting high dissolution immediately after compression, has shown a significantly reduced dissolution after storage. F3 formulation before storage has given a dissolution of 72% and after storage only 51% drug could dissolve at the end of 30 minutes. This could be because of the drug undergoing a transformation to crystalline state during storage. This is verified by the x ray diffraction study (Fig 3) in which it is evident that some sharp diffraction peaks have reappeared (Fig 3 E). Whereas the formulation F2, after storage has not shown any major peaks (Fig 3 D) suggesting that gelucire which is in the formulation is able to offer protection to the amorphous tenoxicam and did not allow any change in the physical state of the drug. Also there is no decrease in the extent of dissolution in case of formulation F2. Thus in between gelucire and HPC, gelucire is able to better protect the amorphous drug. The presence of gelucire in the formulation provides a matrix in which the amorphous drug is embedded minimizing the recrystallization process. In addition, gelucire itself promotes the dissolution of poorly soluble drugs which might have also contributed to the increased dissolution.

Fig 6 Dissolution of tenoxicam from formulated tablets before storage.

Fig 7 Dissolution of tenoxicam from formulated tablets after storage.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has shown that complexation of tenoxicam in SBE₇ β-CD has significantly enhanced the dissolution of the drug. The findings of the investigation showed that the freeze drying method resulted in higher degree of amorphous form of tenoxicam suggesting the formation of better dissolving inclusion complexes between TX and SBE₇ β-CD. The DSC and XRD studies revealed that the drug is present in an amorphous state in the inclusion complex. The inclusion complex could be easily converted into tablet formulations either by melt granulation or direct compression. The resulting tablets showed satisfactory pharmaceutical properties and good dissolution. Of the 2 hydrophilic polymers used in the formulation gelucire is able to better offer protection in preventing the transformation of the amorphous drug during compression and storage. Thus, the results of the present study indicate that the method of preparing complexes is important in enhancing the dissolution rate and inclusion of hydrophilic polymers such as gelucire in the formulation of the high dissolving amorphous forms will ensure the physical stability and high dissolution of the drug. Future research should envisage exploration on newer stabilizing excipients that can be included in the formulation of fast dissolving dosage forms

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Conflict of interest

The authors express no conflict of interest in the research work carried out

List of abbreviations

SBE ₇ -β-CD	– Sulfo butyl ether beta cyclodextrin
HPC	– Hydroxy propyl cellulose
XRD	– X – ray diffraction
DSC	– Differential scanning calorimetry
FTIR	– Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
D.E	– Dissolution efficiency

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